

NUMERICAL OBJECT RINGS PATH PLANNING ALGORITHM

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Abstract

A Numerical Object Rings Path Planning Algorithm (NORPPA) is a heuristic search approach to path finding for Autonomous Robotic Systems. Most traditional methods of this type of path finding are analytical approaches such as the Potential Field, Free Space Configuration, and Vertex Graphs. Analytical techniques use repetitive mathematical calculations with few or no heuristic search techniques [2]. The mathematical routines are applied repetitively until the final goal is accomplished. The advantage of these techniques is that the result is usually unique. The disadvantage of this technique is that the procedure is case-independent. The Heuristic Search technique is used for the development of the NORPPA. This technique employs the rule-of-thumb strategies to help solve problems [1]. The NORPPA uses intelligent schemes to reduce the search space, that is, to prune the logic tree [3,4]. There is no guarantee that a unique solution for a given problem will be reached, only that a correct solution will be found and identified with an execution time that does not exponentially increase with the complexity of the path. The NORPPA includes Means-End-Analysis and Hill Climbing techniques [5,6].

The NORPPA consists of a number of specific task oriented algorithms, which are coordinated by a central program called the Execution Sequencer (ES). The ES interfaces with other functions of the robotic system such as the perception system and drive mechanism. Functionally, the path finding procedure of the NORPPA goes through three stages: (1) the primary path, (2) the refined path, and (3) the travelable path procedures. The primary path procedure is the first draft of the path between the current position and ending, or goal, position. The second stage of the path finding procedure develops a refined path. This path accounts for the starting position, all obstacles encountered, and the ending position. The result is a smooth path that connects the starting and ending positions. The final stage of the procedure is to determine the actual path, called the travelable path. The travelable path procedure selects a portion of the refined path that falls into the local sensing region of the robot. The average path finding execution time of the Primary Path routine simulations for paths ranging from simple (a few bends) to complex paths (larger than ten bends) is about 11.5 seconds using a 486 personal computer at 33 MHZ clock speed. In a comparison to the heuristic approach, the analytical algorithm is dominated by the factor n^n , where n is the number of bends in the path, the analytical algorithm proved to be fast for paths with a small number of bends (small n) and impractically slow for a large number of bends.

Overview of the NORPPA and the Robotic System

The NORPPA is controlled by a central program named Execution Sequencer(ES). The ES determines the flow of the execution of algorithms by calling the Primary, Refined and the Travelable Path routines.

A. Execution Sequencer: Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the ES program. The ES starts with the Primary Path routine and repeats the Refined Path routine until the final goal is achieved. This routine also determines whether the final goal has been achieved. The Primary and the Refined path procedures are discussed in the following sections. The ES also orchestrates the data exchange among peripheral devices such as the Scanning system, Updating system, and the Servo planning system. The Scanning Module (SCM) is a scanning system that will provide the NORPPA with the obstacle map of the environment. The Servo Planning Module (SPM) translates the path selected by the NORPPA into the control signals that control the drive mechanism. The Updating Module (UPM) updates the position of the robot based on the external references. This module is necessary to correct the position calculated by the NORPPA.

Figure 1 - Execution Sequencer Block Diagram

B. Primary Path: The primary path routine limits the search space to the area directly between the start and goal position. This area will be further investigated when an obstacle in this area is detected. It maps all the obstacles known to date in the global environment and applies the Numerical Object Rings routine to the entire global environment. This will result in a path from the starting position to the goal position without further processing such as scanning for new obstacles.

C. Refined Path: The Refined Path routine is the second stage of the NORPPA. By the time the Refined Path routine is called by the ES, the Primary Path routine has already determined a complete path from the start to the goal position based on all obstacles known to the algorithm. The Refined Path routine determines an intermediate goal position using the given Primary Path. It then applies a routine similar to the Primary Path from the current position to the intermediate goal position.

If the robot is traveling in an environment that has not been mapped previously, the primary path calculated by the Primary Path routine is a straight path connecting the starting and the goal positions. This means that the robot does not have a global picture of the environment, and it is detecting obstacles as it travels toward the goal, relying only on its local sensory system. This path finding is referred to as Blind Path finding. Since the local sensory system is limited in range, the robot has no way of knowing a proper direction when it is faced with a large obstacle. Figure 2 illustrates the Blind path finding. As far as the robot is concerned, it is facing a wall-like obstacle with no end in either directions. This is a different path finding problem than is used when the positions of all obstacles are known to the robot. The BLIND mode path finding with the NORPPA is possible because of the way NORPPA is separated into individual routines.

Figure 2- Blind Path Finding With A Large Obstacle

D. Travelable Path: This routine is called after each Refined Path routine. The purpose of this routine is to ensure that the executable path is within the local sensory range or the present active window. Since the active window contains the most recent obstacle information, the chances of obstacle collision is minimized when traveling in this window. The Travelable Path routine uses the Local Path algorithm. The Local Path algorithm receives the refined path and selects a portion of the path that falls within the active window. After the refined path from the current position to the intermediate goal position is determined, this path is sent to the Travelable Path routine. The Travelable Path routine selects a portion of this path that falls within the local sensory range and sends this path to the Servo Planning module to be executed. If the proximity sensors detect a new obstacle during the path execution, the ES interrupts the Path Execution, the current position is saved, and the Refined Path routine will plan a new course. In this case, the Refined Path back tracks a predetermined distance, and then it will follow its normal

routine. If the path is executed successfully to its goal, the ES calls on the Refined Path routine for the next sub-goal position. This routine is repeated until the final goal is achieved.

DISCUSSION OF ALGORITHMS

A. Environmental Setup: It is necessary to define the NORPPA's environment before the discussion of the individual algorithms. This environment is shared by all algorithms and is a medium where the outside information, such as the location of obstacles, are interpreted in a two dimensional system. Consider a rigid object A, moving in an Euclidean two-dimensional space E called the workspace among fixed obstacles $B_i, i=1, \dots, q$.

Both A and B_i 's are closed region in E (See Figure 3). A standard Cartesian coordinate frame, denoted by F_e , is embedded in E. The origin of F_e , denoted by O_e , is called the reference point of E. Another Cartesian frame, denoted by F_a , is embedded in A.

Figure 3 - The Workspace E And The Scratchpad F_a .

The origin of F_a , denoted by O_a , is called the reference point of A. The corresponding axes of F_a and F_e are parallel. The F_e coordinate frame establishes a space that is used by the algorithms to read or write obstacle positions. This space is called the Scratchpad space. Figure 3 shows the workspace E and the Scratchpad space. The F_a coordinate frame is used mainly to identify the heading of the robot in F_e . The configuration of A is identified by parameters X_a, Y_a, PO_a , where X_a and Y_a are the coordinates of A in F_e and $PO_a \{1..16\}$ is the orientation of A in F_e . Since the axes of F_e and F_a frames are parallel, the orientation of the object A is identical in both frames. The 360 degree angle around O_a is divided into 16 incremental angles with steps of 22.5 degrees each.

The configuration space is divided into equal size square cells in a two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate frame. The size of the cell determines the resolution of the configuration space. It also affects the degree of the computation and the accuracy of the path. If the chosen size of the cell is too small, expensive

computations will reduce the efficiency of the algorithm. If the chosen size of the cell is too large, the paths will become inaccurate and the robot can collide with obstacles on sharp turns. The area covered by the robot or an obstacle is the sum of all the cells occupied by it. This sum includes both fully or partially occupied cells which is called the "Area Of The Occupancy" of the robot or an obstacle. Since the object's area of the occupancy is measured by the number of cells, one needs to choose a cell size which is appropriate for a particular environment. As a general rule, a cell size in which the robot's area of occupancy is defined by one cell is recommended.

B. Communication Link among Algorithms: Every algorithm functions independently and communicates with other algorithms with a number of parameters. Figure 4 shows a graphical model that can be applied to all algorithms to describe these parameters.

Figure 4 - Graphical Representation Of Communication Between Two Agents.

C. Position Algorithm: The Position algorithm determines the orientation of the robot in the global environment E. The parameter format for this algorithm is,

$$POSITION[X_{1e}, Y_{1e}, X_{2e}, Y_{2e}, PO, \alpha]$$

where

$$X_{1e}, Y_{1e}, X_{2e}, Y_{2e}$$

are the input parameters and

$$PO, \alpha$$

are the output parameters. Input parameters are the coordinates of two points in the environment E. Most often $[X_{1e}, Y_{1e}]$ is the current position coordinates of the robot and $[X_{2e}, Y_{2e}]$ is the sub-goal position coordinates. The variable "PO" is a constant between one and sixteen which indicates the direction of the robot. This direction is represented in Figure 5, by 16 orientational vectors on the F_a frame. The variable α is a positive number and also contains information about the orientational vectors. This variable is used internally in the Position algorithm for the determination of PO and, also, is provided externally for other algorithms to use. The first breakdown of the orientation is to reduce the options to one of four quadrants. The four quadrants are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5 - Vectors One Through Sixteen Represent The Orientation Of The Robot In F_e .

Figure 6 - Two Cartesian Coordinates F_e And F_a And Their Origins O_e And O_a .

The variable α is used to further determine the exact orientation of the robot. To find variable α , the coordinates of the two given points are used:

$$\Delta_X = X_{2e} - X_{1e}$$

$$\Delta_Y = Y_{2e} - Y_{1e}$$

$$\alpha = \left| \frac{\Delta_Y}{\Delta_X} \right|$$

If $\alpha = 1$, then the vector is 45 degrees within the quadrant. If $\alpha > 1$, the vector is closer to the Y axis and if $\alpha < 1$, the vector

is closer to the X axis. This breaks down each quadrant into three segments. The twelve segments of four quadrants plus four positions between quadrants will bring the total to sixteen segments.

D. Active Window: The Active Window is the area of the environment E that is scanned by the robot's sensors. There is a high degree of confidence about the presence or the absence of obstacles in this window. The size and the shape of the window are determined by the nature of the scanning system. The "Travelable Path" is a path inside this window. This constitutes a reliability factor that increases the integrity of the chosen path. A square active window is chosen to simplify the calculation of the window coordinates. The border lines of this window are determined by the "Window Edge" algorithm.

E. Window Edge Algorithm: The Window Edge algorithm determines the position of the left bottom point and the size of a window and passes them to the calling agent. The window is square and therefore is defined by the coordinates of the left bottom point and the size of one side. The shape of the window is dependent upon the obstacle detection hardware in the scanning system. Depending on the configuration and the density of sensors on the robot, a particular geometric shape will be appropriate. One can choose a semi-circular window and communicate the size and the orientation of the window with a radius and an angle respectively. A square window is chosen for simplicity of calculation. Hence, the Window Edge algorithm is going to find the most bottom left coordinates of the window denoted by X_{lbw} , Y_{lbw} and the size denoted by S. The Window Edge algorithm communicates to the calling agent via five parameters, X_1 , Y_1 , X_2 , Y_2 , and S. The following is the parameter format of the Window Edge algorithm:

$$WindowEdge[X_1, Y_1, X_2, Y_2, S]$$

X_1 and Y_1 hold two different sets of information depending upon whether it is used as an input or output. As an input, X_1 and Y_1 are the coordinates of the first point in F_e . As an output, X_1 and Y_1 are the most bottom left coordinates of the window in F_e .

X_2 and Y_2 are input parameters and represent the X and Y coordinates of the second point in F_e . The variable S holds two different sets of information. As an input, S is a binary switch containing 0 or 1. When S is zero, the window size is determined by the two points X_1 , Y_1 and X_2 , Y_2 . The minimum window size is the active window of the robot, and its size is determined by the range of the robot's local sensory system. When S is 1, the window size is the default value. As an output, S holds the size of the window.

The multiple uses of parameters make this algorithm multifunctional. For example, the Numerical Object Rings algorithm uses $S=0$, when calling the Window Edge to find a window between any two points. The ES uses this algorithm with the switch $S=1$ to find the next active window. The window needs to be positioned in the direction in which the

path is going to be determined. This is analogous to turning one's head to look in a particular direction. The Window Edge algorithm utilizes the parameter α from the Position algorithm to position the window in the proper direction.

F. Numerical Object Rings Algorithm: The Numerical Object Rings algorithm creates a numeric field around those obstacles which have been detected by the scanning system. The numeric field consists of n number of rings surrounding the obstacles. Theoretically, n can be very large; but, since the determination of rings is a time consuming calculation, n should be selected wisely to keep the processing time down. The number of rings should be determined by investigating the resolution of the environment E. An outermost ring is selected as the traveling ring. When the robot encounters this ring, it follows the ring to go around the obstacle. The selection of the traveling ring also determines a proximity cost factor for the path. The traveling ring determines how close or how far the robot gets to obstacles when it is moving around them. Given the ring 4 ($n=4$) and the occupancy of the robot in F_e is one cell, then the closest the robot ever gets to an object is,

$$r \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = 0.707r$$

where r is the length of the cell. Figure 7 shows an obstacle and the Numerical rings surrounding it. The parameter format for the Numerical Rings algorithm is,

$$NumericField[X_1, Y_1, X_2, Y_2]$$

The input parameters X_1 , Y_1 , X_2 , and Y_2 are the coordinates of two points in F_e representing the lower left and the upper right of a window, where the numeric rings will be calculated.

Figure 7 - Numerical Rings Around An Obstacle

The Scratch Pad is the space in F_e frame in which all detected

obstacles and the numeric rings are marked. The boundary of the numeric rings window is calculated by calling the Window Edge algorithm.

Every time the Numerical Object Rings algorithm is activated, the algorithm receives the current Scratch Pad which has been marked in the previous processing. The Numerical Object Rings algorithm uses another algorithm called Clean to clear all previous markings. The algorithm then starts with an unmarked Scratch Pad. The Numerical Object Rings algorithm scans the Scratch Pad environment along the X and Y axes and marks obstacles as it finds them. There are four scans along each axis which mark half of the four object rings around each obstacle. First scan marks the first ring, second scan marks the second ring, etc. This process is repeated for all rings.

G. Straight Path Algorithm: The Straight Path algorithm calculates a straight path between any two given points in the environment E. The parameter format is

StraightPath [ρ , 2, PathArray(),
 X_a, Y_a, X_b, Y_b]

where, $X_a, Y_a, X_b,$ and Y_b are input parameters and they represent the coordinates of the two points in F_e frame. The parameter ρ and the number 2 are the dimensions of PathArray(). The output parameter PathArray() contains the straight Path coordinates. The elements of the array are the X coordinates, located at

$$PathArray(X_i, 1) \Big|_{i=0}^{\rho}$$

and Y coordinates, located at

$$PathArray(Y_i, 2) \Big|_{i=0}^{\rho}$$

Variable ρ is the pointer of the array, and its maximum value is the size of the array. The orientation of the given points (from point one to point two) is determined by calling the Position algorithm. The variable α is used to determine the coordinates of the straight path depending on the orientation. The upper limit ρ is determined by the range of the path, Δ_x or Δ_y , depending on the orientation of the two points.

$$\Delta_x = |X_b - X_a|$$

$$\Delta_y = |Y_b - Y_a|$$

H. Find-a-path Algorithm: The Find-A-Path algorithm finds a collision free path from the current position to the goal/subgoal position. It may be used upon the Primary Path (goal) or the refined path (subgoal). The parameter format for the Path algorithm is

Path [ρ , 2, SPathArray(), σ , 2, Fpath(), bad]

The input parameter SPathArray() is a $\rho \times 2$ array and contains the straight path coordinates of the path from current position to the goal/subgoal position. The current position is located at

$$X_{current} = SPath(1,1)$$

$$Y_{current} = SPath(1,2)$$

and the goal/subgoal position is located at,

$$X_{goal} = SPath(\rho,1)$$

$$Y_{goal} = SPath(\rho,2)$$

The variable "bad" is used as an input when the algorithm is called, and it is used as an output parameter when the algorithm returns. As an input, when bad=0, it indicates that the previous path finding was complete. A complete path stretches from the current position to the sub/subgoal position. The input value of bad \neq 0, indicates that the previous path finding was not complete.

The output parameter FPath() is a $\sigma \times 2$ array containing the collision free path coordinates. This path is qualified by the value of the "bad" parameter. If bad=0, then the path is complete. The first position in the array contains the coordinates of the current position, and the last position in the array contains the coordinates of the goal/subgoal position. If bad \neq 0, then the path position is incomplete. For example, when the robot is facing a wall for a first time, the Find-a-Path algorithm sends a path to the calling agent with a non-zero value of the "bad."

The calling agent sends the straight path array and a pointer(ρ) to the Find-a-Path algorithm. The first and the last coordinates on this array indicate the current and the goal/subgoal position respectively. The scratch pad has been prepared to show the current obstacles and numerical rings. The Find-a-Path algorithm follows the straight path from the current position to the goal/subgoal position and records every collision free point into an array. When a traveling ring is encountered, it follows the ring around the object and back to the straight path. The algorithm always tries to find two alternate routes and selects the shorter of the two. If neither of the searches on the field are successful such as when the robot is facing a wall, the algorithm selects the path based on the following conditions: If the previous path finding session was completed,(input bad=0), then it selects the path which has an orientation closer to the goal orientation and raises the flag bad \neq 0. If the previous path finding session was not completed, (input bad \neq 0), then it selects the path that has an orientation closer to the previous path, with the hope of going around the wall, and raises the flag bad \neq 0. This process is continued until the goal/subgoal position is reached. If the goal/subgoal position is not reached, an error flag is raised and the result is sent to the caller.

I. Intermediate Algorithm: The Intermediate algorithm determines an intermediate goal position by investigating the primary path. These intermediate goal positions make the final path smoother. Figure 8 illustrates the Intermediate Goal algorithm.

Figure 8 - Intermediate Goal Algorithm

The algorithm looks ahead on the primary path at predefined distance intervals. For instance, if the distance interval is selected to be three, it examines every third position in front of the current position on the primary path. Figure 8 shows four paths #1 - 4. Path one is the first interval and path four is the fourth interval. After selecting each interval, the algorithm draws a straight line from the current position to the selected interval point. If this path does not intersect the outer numerical ring, then the next interval position is selected and tested in the same manner. This process continues until the straight path intersects with a numeric ring. The algorithm then backs up one interval to the previous position and selects this point as a first intermediate goal position. Path number four intersects with the numeric ring; therefore, interval three is the next intermediate goal position. This path is guaranteed to be an efficient one, since there is a clear straight path to this sub-goal.

J. Local Path Planning Algorithm: The Local Path Planning algorithm receives the path from the current position to the intermediate goal position and selects the portion of the path which falls inside the active window. This path is then sent to the Servo Module to be executed. This algorithm ensures that the robot will never travel in the unmapped regions of the environment.

COST FUNCTIONS

The cost functions are used to measure the quality of a path. Some algorithms find an approximate path and apply a cost function to optimize it. Some algorithms use a relaxation method to minimize the total cost by applying the cost function to an approximate path. The NORPPA uses the logical arguments within different algorithms to enforce the following four cost functions:

A. Proximity to the Object: This cost is a measure of how close the vehicle should get to an object when encountering it. This function is executed in the Numerical Object Rings algorithm.

B. Path Will Never Travel in an Unmapped Region: This function is executed in the Local Planning algorithm.

C. Shortest Distance of the Path: This function is executed in the Primary Path algorithm.

D. Straightness of the Path: The efficiency of the path improves from the primary path to the calculated path. This function is executed in the ES.

SUMMARY

The NORPPA is based on heuristic programming similar to the inference engines of most expert systems. Unlike Voronoi-based locus methods, the execution time of the path does not have an exponential relation to the number of bends in the path. This enables the NORPPA to find quick collision free paths for difficult path finding conditions. There are a minimum number of decisions made for every path finding session with the NORPPA, therefore there is a minimum execution time for the simplest paths. The NORPPA's execution time ranges from five to ninety seconds for simple to difficult paths respectively. Voronoi-based algorithms' execution time under similar conditions starts from fractions of seconds for the simple paths but quickly grows to several hours of calculation for paths with larger numbers of bends ($n > 10$). The Multi-Processing Mobile Autonomous Robotic System (MP_MARS) based on the Numerical Object Rings Path Planning Algorithm (NORPPA) is a new approach to path planning. MP_MARS is the whole robotic system that includes the navigation, the perception, the mechanical and the drive systems. NORPPA was evaluated by an independent government agency for its applicability for military application and was rated as a very high interest for mine hunting and mine avoidance in uncharted environments.

REFERENCES

1. Farreny, Henri. AI and expertise: Heuristic Search, inference automatic proving. New York: Halsted, 1989.
2. Mount, David M. ON Finding Shortest Paths On Convex Polyhedra. Maryland, University of Maryland, 1985.
3. Benton, John R. "Hierarchical Route Finder." Report R-139, U.S. Army Engineer Topographic Laboratories, Fort Belvoir, Virginia. June 1988.
4. Puri, Sunil. Two Dimensional Path Planning with obstacles and Shadows. Maryland, University of Maryland, 1987.
5. Martin, James. Building Expert Systems: A Tutorial. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice Hall, 1990.
6. Quek, Francis K.H. A Decision System for Autonomous Robot Navigation over Rough Terrain. Ann Arbor: Environmental Research Institute of Michigan, 1985.